

**Studies in Optical Rotation. Rotatory Powers of
Acidyl-biscamphorquinonehydrazones and
Camphorylthiocarbamyldrazides
and Attempts to Prepare
Compounds Possessing
Abnormal Rotation.**

By M. S. KOTNIS, B. SANJIVA RAO AND P. C. GUHA.

Section A.

In an attempt to correlate the effect of chemical constitution with optical rotatory power, Frankland (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 654) has observed that molecular rotation of a homologous series changes gradually until a maximum is reached and then declines or remains constant. Hilditch (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 1578) found that in the menthyl esters of the aliphatic dibasic acids, there is a decrease of rotation in passing from the first to the second and after that an increase up to the fifth (adipic); whereas, in the case of the brucine salts the value goes on increasing up to the third and from there decreases *via* fourth up to the fifth (Table I). The anomalous rotation of the oxalic acid derivatives, particularly in the brucine salt series, is probably due to the contiguity of two carboxylic groups. Evidently, Hilditch's results are not in conformity with Frankland's observation and hence it seemed desirable to follow up the study of the dibasic acids further.

As the menthyl esters and the brucine salts of these acids have been examined by Hilditch (*loc. cit.*), it seemed desirable to study an entirely different class of derivatives of these acids and compare the results with those obtained by him. Besides the camphorquinone derivative of the five hydrazides—oxalic to adipic, three more *viz.*, those of carbo-, terephthalic and isophthalic have also been prepared for the sake of comparison. Table I gives the values of $[\alpha]_{5893}$ and $[M]_{5893}$ for 2½ and 5% solutions of the menthyl esters and brucine salts as observed by Hilditch while the values for $[\alpha]$ and $[M]$ now obtained for acidylcamphorquinonehydrazones with both green and yellow mercury lines, are given in Table II.

TABLE I.

Acid.	l-Menthyl esters				Brucine salts			
	2.5%		5.0%		5.0%		2.5%	
	$[\alpha]_D$	$[M]_D$	$[\alpha]_D$	$[M]_D$	$[\alpha]_D$	$[M]_D$	$[\alpha]_D$	$[M]_D$
Oxalic	-103.4	-378.4	-104.0	-380.6	3.0	26.3	2.8	24.6
Malonic	-79.54	-302.6	-79.24	-301.1	52.76	470.6	52.76	470.6
Succinic	-82.40	-324.6	-81.90	-322.7	65.80	591.6	64.12	580.9
Glutaric	-80.16	-327.1	-80.26	-329.3	50.62	465.8	50.40	464.4
Adipic	-83.60	-352.8	-83.80	-353.6	42.80	399.2	42.60	397.8

TABLE II.

Camphorquinone hydrazones.	M. p.	$[\alpha]_D$	$[M]_D$	$[\alpha]_D$	$[M]_D$	Disp. coeff.	$[M]_D/[\alpha]_D$
Carbo	22.5°	286.6	1106	334.4	1290		1.17
Oxalic	249	256.1	1060	298.6	1237		1.18
Malonic	185	251.3	1075	272.1	1165		1.08
Succinic	275	—	—	—	—		—
Glutaric	219	213.7	970.3	261.2	1186		1.22
Adipic	220	195.4	914.7	260.7	1220		1.33

FIG. 1.

Sp. Rotations of acidyl biscamphorquinone-hydrazones.

FIG. 2.

Mol. Rotations of acidyl biscamphorquinone-hydrazones.

It will be observed from Table II as well as from Fig. 1 that the specific rotations of the different substances fall sharply from carbo-biscamphorquinonehydrazone to the corresponding oxalic compound

and then gradually decrease along the series. This is rather contrary to Hilditch's observation of a second maximum with the adipic compound. Coming to the molecular rotation, however, the case is not so simple (*cf.* Fig. 2), because the malonic compound has a higher molecular rotation than the oxalic for the yellow light. Similarly, the glutaric derivative just exceeds the corresponding malonic compound in its molecular rotation for the green light. It was rather unfortunate that the succinic hydrazide should have yielded an insoluble compound, its rotation thus remaining unascertained; the general fall in the specific as well as molecular rotation is, however, quite distinct. The molecular rotations as observed in this series go to support Frankland's view.

The dispersion coefficient varies between 1.08 and 1.83. The use of these data for the calculation of the dispersion curves of optically active compounds of a homologous series has been recorded by Hagenback (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1915, **89**, 570). The constancy of the coefficient of dispersive power was observed also by Rupe (*Annalen*, 1915, **409**, 327) who obtained $\alpha_F/\alpha_D = 2.31$ for methylenecamphors of the type

In order to determine the effect of concentration on the specific rotation and rotatory dispersion, the rotation of carbonyl-biscamphorquinonehydrazone under various concentrations have been studied. The choice of the carbohydrazide derivative for this purpose is only due to its yielding fairly soluble compounds with both camphorquinone and camphoryl mustard oil.

TABLE III.

Effect of concentration on the rotation of carbonyl-biscamphorquinonehydrazone.

G. in 100 c.c.	$[\alpha]_D$	$[M]_D$	$[\alpha]_F$	$[M]_F$	Disp. coeff. $[\alpha]_F/[\alpha]_D$
0.0495	316.0	1220	406.2	1568	1.29
0.0886	316.0	1220	395.0	1525	1.25
0.1830	319.6	1234	383.6	1480	1.20
0.1773	318.8	1230	375.2	1448	1.18
0.2216	320.4	1237	368.4	1403	1.18

FIG. 3.

Change of specific rotation with concentration. Carbonyl-biscamphorquinonehydrazone in alcohol.

From Table III it will be observed that the specific rotation gradually drops with increasing concentration for the green light (Fig. 3), with the yellow light it is, however, fairly constant.

Section B.

In section A, the various observations made about the optical rotatory power of camphorquinonehydrazones (I) of the dibasic acids have been described. In this part, it is proposed to take up another set of compounds

viz., the camphorylthiocarbamyl hydrazides (II) of the same acids.

(I)

(II)

As there are two sulphur atoms attached to two carbon atoms in the chain between the camphor and the dibasic acid residue it was expected to exert some influence on the rotatory power of these compounds. A study of the optical rotatory powers of compounds of this series and a comparison with those already obtained for the corresponding camphorquinonehydrazones has, therefore, been made.

TABLE IV.

Biscamphorylthiocarbamylhydrazides.

Biscamphoryl- thiocarbamyl hydrazides	M. p.	$[\alpha]_D$	$[M]_D$	$[\alpha]_G$	$[M]_G$	Dispersion coeff. $[M]_G/[M]_D$
Carbo	208°	28.2	143.2	32.9	167.1	1.17
Oxalic	245	30.4	162.9	50.7	271.7	1.67
Malonic	185	29.8	169.9	50.7	278.9	1.70
Succinic	275	39.7	224.0	50.5	284.8	1.27
Glutaric	201	12.4	71.7	18.6	107.5	1.50
Adipic	207	33.4	197.7	42.4	251.0	1.27

FIG. 4.

Specific rotation of biscamphorylthiocarbamylhydrazides.

FIG. 5.

Molecular rotation of biscamphorylthiocarbamylhydrazides.

Table IV gives the values for the specific and molecular rotations as well as rotatory dispersion and dispersion coefficients of these

compounds. The first point that strikes one is the lower rotatory powers of these compounds compared with those of the camphorquinonehydrazones. This is not peculiar to these series of compounds alone, it being well known that introduction of a sulphur atom in the camphor derivatives generally lowers the rotatory power of the compound to a very great extent (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 115; 1907, 91, 1886; *J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1927, 10A, 33). As seen from Fig. 4, the specific rotation curve of these compounds is anything but regular. For the yellow light, the curve rises a little from the carbo to the oxalic hydrazide but again declines to a slight extent for the malonic compound. The specific rotation then jumps up in the case of the succinic followed by a steep decline for the glutaric hydrazide. Finally with the adipic compound the curve again rises up, the specific rotation assuming a value in the neighbourhood of those for the first two members of the series. This alternation is also observed in the case of the melting points of these hydrazides. With the green light, however, the specific rotation rises steeply from carbo to oxalic and is practically constant for oxalic, malonic and succinic compounds though the rest of the curve runs parallel to that for the yellow light. The curves for the molecular rotation (Fig. 5) are more or less similar to those for the specific rotation for the corresponding light. Thus it will be seen that the curves for the specific or molecular rotation of the biscamphorylthiocarbamylhydrazides show practically no similarity with those of the corresponding camphorquinonehydrazones. This can be attributed mainly to the presence of sulphur atoms in the compound. The values for the dispersion coefficient for the compounds fluctuate between 1.70 to 1.27.

TABLE V.

Effect of concentration on rotation: Biscamphorylthiocarbamyl-carbohydrazide.

G. in 100 c.c.	$[\alpha]_y$.	$[M]_y$.	$[\alpha]_g$.	$[M]_g$.	Disp. coeff. $[\alpha]_g / [\alpha]_y$.
0.0425	—	—	23.5	119.4	
0.0850	21.2	107.6	27.4	139.2	1.15
0.1275	24.7	125.5	28.6	145.3	1.16
0.1700	26.4	134.2	30.2	153.4	1.14
0.2125	28.2	142.7	32.9	166.5	1.17

Table V contains the values obtained for the specific rotation of biscamphorylthiocarbamylcarbohydrazide with solutions of

FIG. 6.

Change of specific rotation with concentration of biscamphorylthiocarbamylcarbohydrazide in alcohol.

various concentrations. The curves for the same (Fig. 6) run practically parallel to one another. Moreover, the rotation increases with concentration in agreement with Hilditch's observation *viz.*, the specific rotations of the menthyl esters and brucine salts of the oxalic acid series are greater for a 5% solution than for a 2.5% solution. This forms another point of contrast between the camphorquinonehydrazones and camphorylthiocarbamylhydrazides (*cf.* Fig. 3). Coming to the question of the dispersion coefficient it will be observed

that it is practically constant for the solutions of all concentrations. As the solutions of camphorylidene-carbohydrazide reveal the same fact, it might be safely deduced that the dispersion coefficient has a constant value for any particular compound.

Section C.

In this laboratory, Patel and Guha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 87) have prepared 1:4-naphthylenebisiminobenzylidene-imino-camphor containing 17 double bonds and having $[M]_D = 22000^\circ$. It was sought to extend the work further by preparing a few more compounds likely to possess high molecular rotation. The following compounds, *viz.*, (a) camphorquinonehydrazone of benzaldehyde-*p*-iminocamphor, (b) *terephthaldiamido-bis-phenylene-4:4*-iminocamphor, (c) 9:10-phenanthraquinol-2:7-bisiminocamphor, (d) camphoriminonaphthalene-4-azo-*p*-camphoriminobenzene, (e) 1:1'-dinaphthylurea-4:4'-bisiminocamphor, possessing all or most of the characteristics required for abnormal rotation (*cf.* Forster and Spinner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 889) were expected to show high molecular rotation.

Difficulties were encountered in the preparation of most of these compounds. The preparation of (a) from *p*-camphoryliminobenzaldehyde or from camphorylhydrazone of *p*-aminobenzaldehyde was not possible as neither camphorquinone nor its hydrazone condensed with *p*-aminobenzaldehyde due perhaps to the latter being polymerised (Walther and Mausch, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1897, 56, 102). The hydrolysis of the acetyl group of *p*-acetaminobenzylidene camphorquinonehydrazone (I), prepared as follows:

could not be effected with dilute alkali, *p*-acetaminobenzaldehyde and camphor being obtained; with dilute acids, the products being azocamphanone and *p*-aminobenzaldehyde.

The preparation of the diamine by de-acetylating *terephthalyl*-bis-*p*-acetphenylenediamine (II) was not possible as during de-acetylation the molecule broke up into *terephthalic* acid and *p*-phenylenediamine. Attempts to reduce *terephthalyldi-p*-nitroaniline (III) or di-*p*-azobenzene-*terephthalyldiamide* (IV) to obtain the same amine also failed.

2:7-Diamino-9:10-phenanthraquinol required for compound (c) was prepared according to Kessman and Wense (*Ber.*, 1885, 18, 2169) but neither this nor aminonaphthalene-4-azo-*p*-aminobenzene required for the preparation of (d) could be condensed with camphorquinone.

The hydrochloride of *pp*-diaminodinaphthylurea (VI) obtained by reduction of the corresponding dinitro compound (V) which was in its turn obtained by condensing 1:4-nitronaphthylamine with phenyl carbonate, gave with potassium cyanate, the expected dicarbamido-

dinaphthylurea (VII). The condensation of the hydrochloride with camphorquinone, though tried under varying conditions of experiments, gave only a brownish tarry resinous mass from which the resinous compound (e) could not be isolated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Section A.

The dihydrazides of oxalic, malonic, succinic, glutaric, adipic, terephthalic and isophthalic acids were prepared by the action of hydrazine hydrate on their ethyl esters. Carbohydrazide was prepared by the action of hydrazine hydrate on phenylcarbonate (Cazeneuve and Moreau, *Compt. rend.*, 1899, 129, 1255). The camphorquinone compounds of the dihydrazides were readily obtained by heating concentrated aqueous solution of the former with an alcoholic solution of the latter on a water-bath for 2-4 hours. The camphorylidene hydrazides are generally pale yellow compounds, sparingly soluble in alcohol, much less soluble in other organic solvents.

symCarbobiscamphorquinonehydrazone (R : N·NH·CO·NH·N : R).—Carbohydrazide (1.5 g., 1 mol.) was dissolved in water (5 c.c.) and mixed with a solution of camphorquinone (5.5 g., 2 mol.) in alcohol (25 c.c.) and the mixture heated on a water-bath for 4 hours. The precipitate obtained on dilution with water was crystallised from 50% alcohol in pale yellow needles, m.p. 225°, yield 3 g. (43%). (Found: N, 14.7. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_3\text{N}_4$ requires N, 14.51 per cent). 0.1047 G. of the substance dissolved in 50 c.c. of 95% alcohol gave a rotation of 1.2 (yellow) and 1.40 (green) in a 2 dcm. tube. Hence $[\alpha]_D = 286.6^\circ$ and $[\alpha]_D = 334.4^\circ$ and $[M]_D = 1106$, $[M]_D = 1290$.

symOxalyl-biscamphorquinonehydrazone (R : N—NH—CO—CO—NH—N=R).—Oxalylhydrazide (2 g., 1 mol.), dissolved in a little water, was added to a solution of camphorquinone (5.6 g., 2 mol.) in alcohol. The pale yellow precipitate formed on heating the mixture

for 2 hours was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 249° , yield 5.5 g. (72%). (Found: N, 13.26. $C_{22}H_{30}O_4N_4$ requires N, 13.5 per cent). 0.1172 G. of the substance in 50 c.c. alcohol showed a rotation of 1.2° (yellow), 1.4° (green) in a 2 dcm. tube. Hence $[\alpha]_D = 256.1^{\circ}$, $[\alpha]_G = 298.6^{\circ}$ and $[M]_D = 1060^{\circ}$, $[M]_G = 1237$.

Malonyl-biscamphorquinonehydrazone (I, X = CH_2).—Malonic hydrazide (2.0 g.) and camphorquinone (5.0 g.) gave a pale yellow powder (4 g. or 57%), m.p. 185° . (Found: N, 13.4. $C_{23}H_{32}O_4N_4$ requires N, 13.08 per cent). 0.1194 G. of the substance in 50 c.c. alcohol showed a rotation of 1.2° (yellow) and 1.3° (green) in a 2 dcm. tube; hence $[\alpha]_D = 251.3$, $[\alpha]_G = 272.1$ and $[M]_D = 1075$, $[M]_G = 1165$.

Succinyl-biscamphorquinonehydrazone [I, X = $(CH_2)_2$].—Succinic hydrazide (2 g.) and camphorquinone (4.6 g.) gave 5.5 g. (90%) of a product which was very sparingly soluble in all organic solvents. It was purified by washing with water and boiling alcohol, m.p. 275° . (Found: N, 12.83. $C_{24}H_{34}O_4N_4$ requires N, 12.7 per cent). As the substance is very difficultly soluble, its optical rotation could not be determined.

Glutaryl-biscamphorquinonehydrazone [I, X = $(CH_2)_3$].—Glutaric hydrazide (2 g.) and camphorquinone (4.1 g.) yielded 4 g. (67%) of the product which recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 219° . (Found: N, 12.1. $C_{25}H_{36}O_4N_4$ requires N, 12.28 per cent). 0.1053 G. of the substance showed a rotation of 0.90° and 1.1° for yellow and green light respectively in a 2 dcm. tube and 50 c.c. alcohol; hence $[\alpha]_D = 213.7$, $[\alpha]_G = 261.2$ and $[M]_D = 970.3$, $[M]_G = 1186$.

Adipyl-biscamphorquinonehydrazone [I, X = $(CH_2)_4$] obtained in 50% yield from adipic hydrazide (1 mol.) and camphorquinone (2 mol.) recrystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 220° . (Found: N, 11.8. $C_{26}H_{36}O_4N_4$ requires N, 11.91 per cent). 0.1151 G. of the substance dissolved in 50 c.c. alcohol showed in a 2 dcm. tube a rotation of 0.94° and 1.2° for yellow and green light respectively. Hence $[\alpha]_D = 195.4$, $[\alpha]_G = 260.7$ and $[M]_D = 914.7$, $[M]_G = 1220$.

Terephthalyl-biscamphorquinonehydrazone (I, X = C_6H_4) was prepared from terephthalic hydrazide and camphorquinone, m.p. 279° . (Found: N, 11.59. $C_{28}H_{34}O_4N_4$ requires N, 11.43 per cent). The substance being insoluble, its rotatory power could not be determined.

isoPhthalyl-biscamphorquinonehydrazone melted at 274° after repeatedly boiling with alcohol and water. The rotation could not be determined owing to the sparing solubility of the substance.

Section B.

Camphorylthiocarbamylhydrazides obtained from camphoryl mustard oil and the hydrazides as white precipitates are generally mixed up with some unreacted camphoryl mustard oil from which they could not be easily freed by crystallisation. The best method, is, however, to dissolve these products in a little alcohol and precipitate fractionally by water, the highest melting fractions after one or two crystallisations giving the pure product. They are all very sparingly soluble in solvents like benzene, chloroform, etc. but are fairly soluble in alcohol which furnished a good medium for optical measurements. The specific rotations are much lower than those of the corresponding camphorquinonehydrazones.

Carbonyl-biscamphorylthiocarbamylhydrazide [CO(NH·NH·CS·NH·Y)₂].—A mixture of carbohydrazide (1 mol.) dissolved in a little water and camphorylthiocarbimide (2 mol.) dissolved in alcohol was heated on a water-bath for 4 hours. The precipitate obtained on cooling melted at 155° while the mother liquor yielded on dilution with water a precipitate which was crystallised from alcohol in silvery plates, m.p. 208°. (Found: N, 16·13. C₂₃H₃₆O₃N₆S₂ requires N, 16·54 per cent). [α]_D = 28·2, [α]_D = 32·9 and [M]_D = 143·2, [M]_D = 167·1.)

Oxalyl-biscamphorylthiocarbamylhydrazide
$$\begin{array}{c} \text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{Y} \\ | \\ \text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{Y} \end{array}$$

The precipitate obtained from the reaction mixture on cooling and diluting with a little water melted at 231°, the mother liquor yielding on further dilution, a precipitate, m.p. 200·05°. The first fraction was recrystallised from boiling alcohol in silvery plates, m.p. 245°. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol. (Found: N, 15·8. C₂₄H₃₆O₄N₆S₂ requires N, 15·7 per cent). [α]_D = 30·4, [α]_D = 50·7 and [M]_D = 162·9, [M]_D = 271·7.

Malonyl-biscamphorylthiocarbamylhydrazide (II, X = CH₂).—The precipitate obtained on cooling the reaction mixture after 4 hours' heating melted at 162°. The mother liquor yielded on successive dilution two products, m.p. 151° and 183° respectively, the latter on recrystallisation melted at 185°. A further quantity was obtained by redissolving the fractions, m.p. 162° and 151° in little boiling alcohol and rejecting the unreacted camphoryl mustard oil which

crystallised first; the mother liquor contained the required compound. (Found: N, 15.01. $C_{25}H_{38}O_4N_6S_2$ requires N, 15.27 per cent). $[\alpha]_D = 29.8$, $[\alpha]_D = 50.7$ and $[M]_D = 163.9$, $[M]_D = 278.9$].

Succinyl-biscamphorylthiocarbamylhydrazide [II, X = $(CH_2)_2$].—The product was obtained by precipitating the reaction mixture with water, m.p. 170°. On recrystallisation from dilute alcohol it was obtained in silvery plates, m.p. 176°. [Found: N, 14.7. $C_{26}H_{40}O_4N_6S_2$ requires N, 14.89 per cent). $[\alpha]_D = 39.7$, $[\alpha]_D = 50.5$ and $[M]_D = 224.0$, $[M]_D = 284.8$].

Glutaryl-biscamphorylthiocarbamylhydrazide [II, X = $(CH_2)_3$] was obtained from the mother liquor of the reaction mixture by dilution with water, the crude product melting at 195-98°. The pure compound was obtained by once crystallising from dilute alcohol in light silvery plates, m.p. 201°. (Found: N, 14.66. $C_{27}H_{42}O_4N_6S_2$ requires N, 14.53 per cent). $[\alpha]_D = 12.4$, $[\alpha]_D = 18.6$, $[M]_D = 71.7$, $[M]_D = 107.5$].

Adipyl-biscamphorylthiocarbamylhydrazide [II, X = $(CH_2)_4$] being moderately soluble in alcohol remains in the mother liquor of the reaction mixture and is obtained by precipitating with water. The crude product, m.p. 200-203°, on recrystallisation from dilute alcohol, gave the pure compound as silvery white plates, m.p. 207°. (Found: N, 14.3. $C_{28}H_{44}O_4N_6S_2$ requires N, 14.2 per cent). $[\alpha]_D = 33.4$, $[\alpha]_D = 42.4$, and $[M]_D = 197.7$, $[M]_D = 251.0$].

Action of terephthalyl and isophthalylhydrazides with camphoryl-isothiocyanate.—The reaction products melted at 169° and 206° respectively. As they were almost insoluble in alcohol and other solvents, their rotatory power could not be determined.

Section C.

p-Acetaminobenzylidenecamphorquinone- α -hydrazone (I).—An intimate mixture of *p*-acetaminobenzaldehyde (16 g.) and camphorquinone- α -hydrazone (18 g.) moistened with a little amyl alcohol was heated at 130° in an oil-bath for 3 hours. The reaction product crystallised from alcohol in shining golden yellow needles, m.p. 232°, yield 25 g. The substance is insoluble in water, more soluble in hot alcohol and sparingly soluble in benzene and chloroform. (Found: C, 70.27; H, 7.48; N, 12.85. $C_{19}H_{23}O_2N_3$ requires C, 70.15; H, 7.07; N, 12.92 per cent). The substance (0.2504 g.) dissolved in absolute

alcohol (100 c.c.) gave a rotation of 0.12° in a 5 cm. tube. Hence $[\alpha]_D = 95.85^\circ$ and $[M]_D = 311.6^\circ$.

(i) The *oxime* crystallised from alcohol in yellow rectangular plates, m.p. 183° . The substance (0.1501 g.), dissolved in 95 % alcohol (100 c.c.), gave a rotation of 0.41° in a 5 cm. tube. Hence $[\alpha]_D = 546.3$ and $[M]_D = 1858.0$. (ii) The *semicarbazone* crystallised in fine silky needles from alcohol, m.p. 195° . The substance (0.0976g.) dissolved in 95 % alcohol (100 c.c.) gave a rotation of 0.05° in a 5 cm. tube. Hence $[\alpha]_D = 102.4$ and $[M]_D = 391.4$. (iii) The *phenylhydrazone* crystallised from dilute alcohol as pink leaflets, m.p. 205° . The substance (0.1193 g.) in 95 % alcohol (100 c.c.) gave a rotation of 0.09° in a 5 cm. tube, hence $[\alpha]_D = 150.9$ and $[M]_D = 626.2$.

Hydrolysis of the hydrazone by potassium hydroxide solution gave *p*-acetaminobenzaldehyde (*oxime*, m.p. 207°) and camphor.

Hydrolysis with dilute hydrochloric acid or dilute sulphuric acid gave shining plates, m.p. 219° identified to be azocamphanone.

terePhthalyl-di-p-acetphenylenediamine (II).—To a solution of monoacetphenylenediamine in a little glacial acetic acid, theoretical quantity of *terephthalyl* chloride was added gradually when the solution became warm and a small quantity of a precipitate separated. On heating the mixture for 1 hour at 120° a pasty mass was obtained which was neutralised with sodium carbonate and on being boiled repeatedly with water, gave an amorphous ash-coloured powder insoluble in all the organic solvents, m.p. 350° . (Found: C, 64.9; H, 6.0; N, 12.9. $C_{24}H_{22}O_4N_4$ requires C, 65.35; H, 5.12; N, 13.0 per cent).

terePhthalyl-di-p-nitroaniline (III).—A mixture of *terephthalyl* chloride (1 mol.) and *p*-nitroaniline (4 mol.) was heated on a water-bath for an hour in presence of benzene. The heavy precipitate was filtered and freed from nitroaniline hydrochloride by washing with water. The residue on boiling with alcohol left a yellow amorphous powder insoluble in all the organic solvents, m.p. 295° . (Found: N, 14.0. $C_{20}H_{14}O_6N_4$ requires N, 13.8 per cent). Isolation of the pure diamine by reducing this compound has not been successful.

terePhthalyl-diaminoazobenzene (IV).—A mixture of *terephthalyl* chloride (7.5 g.), *p*-aminoazobenzene (29.0 g.) and benzene (500 c.c.) was heated for 1 hour. An amorphous orange yellow powder was obtained by repeatedly washing the product with water and alcohol. It does not melt even at 325° . (Found: N, 15.99. $C_{32}H_{24}O_2N_4$

requires N, 16.03 per cent). This compound could not be reduced by tin and hydrochloric acid to the desired diamine.

Action of 2:7-diaminophenanthraquinol on camphorquinone.—2:7-Dinitrophenanthraquinone was prepared according to the method of Schmidt and Kampf (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 3739) which was found to be preferable to the methods of Werner (*Annalen*, 1902, 321, 336) and Graebe (*ibid.*, 1873, 167, 143). It was reduced to 2:7-diaminophenanthraquinol by the method of Kleemann and Wense (*Ber.*, 1885, 18, 2169). The following modifications in the method, however, were adopted with advantage: Tin and hydrochloric acid were used instead of stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid as it hastened the reaction and the solution of the tin double salt was concentrated before removing the tin by hydrogen sulphide thus avoiding the oxidation of the amine during concentration. The amine did not condense with camphorquinone.

4:4'-Dinitrodinaphthylurea (V).—1:4-Nitronaphthylamine was prepared by nitration of α -acetnaphthalide (Lellmann and Remy, *Ber.*, 1886, 19, 797) and the separation of the 4-nitro compound effected according to Morgan and Micklethwait (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 928). 1:4-Nitronaphthylamine (14 g.) was intimately mixed with an equal weight of phenylcarbonate and heated in an oil-bath for an hour at 190° and at 210° for one hour more. The unreacted phenyl carbonate and the phenol formed during the reaction were removed by washing with CCl_4 , the insoluble yellow amorphous powder was purified by repeatedly boiling with alcohol, m.p. 275°. (Found: C, 62.7; H, 4.1; N, 14.03. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5\text{N}_4$ requires C, 62.7; H, 3.7; N, 13.93 per cent).

4:4'-Diaminodinaphthylurea (VI).—Dinitrodinaphthylurea (10 g.) was heated under reflux with strong hydrochloric acid (100 c.c.) and granulated tin (63.0 g.) for 6 hours, when almost all the tin went into solution and in place of the yellow dinitro compound a flocculent white precipitate remained suspended in the liquid. After cooling the white precipitate was separated by filtration and purified by crystallisation from a large volume of water as shining plates. It left inorganic residue on incineration and was the stannous chloride double salt of diaminodinaphthylurea hydrochloride. (Found: N, 6.9. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{ON}_3, 2\text{HCl}, 2\text{SnCl}_2$ requires N, 7.0 per cent).

The tin double salt was freed from tin by passing hydrogen sulphide repeatedly in a solution of boiling dilute hydrochloric acid, and the tin-free solution evaporated to dryness in a vacuum when a white

crystalline hydrochloride was left. This, however, on exposure to air rapidly turned pinkish, m.p. above 300° . (Found: N, 11.7.* $C_{21}H_{18}ON_3 \cdot 2HCl$ requires N, 13.5 per cent).

Dicarbamidodinaphthylurea (VII).—To an aqueous solution of the hydrochloride of (VI, 3 g.) was added an aqueous solution of potassium cyanate (1.5 g.) under ice-cooling, and the separated dicarbamido compound crystallised from water, m.p. above 300° . (Found: N, 20.16. $C_{23}H_{20}O_3N_6$ requires N, 19.63 per cent).

Action of diaminodinaphthylurea with camphorquinone.—A mixture of the hydrochloride of diaminodinaphthylurea (2 g.), sodium acetate (1.6 g.) and camphorquinone (1.6 g.) was heated under reflux in an alcoholic suspension for 3 hours when a dark viscous tarry mass separated. Though the desired camphorquinone condensation product (Calc. N, 8.7 per cent.) could not be isolated a yellow crystalline compound, m.p. 185° , was obtained from the tarry reaction product by repeatedly precipitating it with petrol from benzene solution and then crystallising from a large volume of petrol (Found: N, 6.3 per cent. $[\alpha]_D = +0.48^{\circ}$)

DEPARTMENT OF ORGANIC CHEMISTRY,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BANGALORE.

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* The low value of nitrogen is evidently due to the presence of some stannous chloride double salt which could not be completely removed though H_2S was passed for more than one dozen times.

